

STUDENTS' READINESS, IMPLEMENTATION AND ATTITUDE TOWARDS E-LEARNING: IMPACT ON ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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Students' Readiness, Implementation and Attitude Towards E-Learning: Impact on Academic Performance

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Abstract

A study was conducted to determine students' readiness, implementation satisfaction, and attitudes towards e-learning, and its academic impact among first-year Criminology students of Gingoog City Colleges. There were 134 participants in this study. This study adopted a descriptive-correlational-casual design. Pearson product correlation was utilized to ascertain the significant relationship between the students' academic achievement, readiness, implementation satisfaction, and attitudes towards e-learning. At the same time, Multiple Regression Analysis was employed to determine the variable that can best influence academic performance. The study revealed that the participants were moderately ready in the e-learning modality; they were highly satisfied in its implementation; possessed a highly positive attitude towards e-learning, and had a good academic performance. There was no significant relationship between students' academic performance, e-learning readiness, and their satisfaction with e-learning implementation; however, students' attitude on e-learning showed a significant relationship to academic performance in the said subject and emerged as the sole variable that significantly influenced students' academic performance in Social Science. Therefore, it can be inferred that the majority of the students who take part in this study are not totally ready for e-learning; but are highly satisfied with the school's e-learning implementation, and those who have positive attitudes towards e-learning can achieve better performance in Social Science.

Keywords: *academic achievement, attitudes, criminology, e-learning, satisfaction, social science*

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has dramatically affected the academe. It unequivocally forced educational institutions worldwide to cancel the traditional face-to-face mode of classes and adapt to the "new normal" or make flexible learning arrangements to help contain its further spread while continuing learning delivery. As a response to the challenge posed by the pandemic in the realm of education, e-learning is one of the learning modalities considered among tertiary educational institutions for their learning continuity mechanisms. Largely untapped in the Philippines, there is widespread concern about e-learning readiness in infrastructure, adaptation to it by the students, teachers, and the institutions, which may significantly affect the former's academic performance.

Meanwhile, Higher Education Institutions or HEIs in the country were given academic freedom. They should implement available distance learning, e-learning, and other alternative modes of delivery to students as instructed by the Commission on Higher Education amid a pandemic (CHED, 2020). This researcher believes that for the country to fully reap the benefits of the Internet and digital technology in education, it must be harnessed and utilized e-learning. As we are now in the 21st century where learning demands 21st-century skills and technology, the e-learning modality is a great platform where our students can learn even better with internet technology or any digital media with or without the teacher's physical presence.

With the physical limitations brought by the pandemic, the school this researcher has worked with has decided to utilize e-learning as one of its learning modalities for the school year 2020-2021. Initially, it was to adapt a learning management system provided by a third-party vendor. However, due to some technical difficulties that may adversely affect learners' usage of the system, the school decided to forego it and instead used Google Classroom and other Google applications to deliver its classes synchronously and asynchronously. As such, the current COVID-19 pandemic, which compelled educational institutions to shift from traditional face-to-face learning to flexible or e-learning modality, prompted this researcher to investigate the tertiary students' readiness and perceptions on e-learning implementation and its impact on students' academic achievement thus far.

The Center of Educational Research and Innovation, CERI (2005) by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), defined e-learning as the use of information and communications technologies (ICT) to enhance and support learning in tertiary education. For Christie & Ferdos (2004), e-learning in higher education is a technique to enhance learning and teaching experiences used to educate students with or without their instructors through any type of digital media. Dalsgaard (2008) in Penny (2011) pointed out the independence of time, space, and individuality as its significant advantages and that the teacher-centered has changed to a student-centered approach. Since it provides excellent flexibility in many areas, the teaching-learning process transcends the class boundaries. Therefore, the physical limits of education are overcome, and learning is possible anywhere (Okhovati et al., 2005) as cited by (Rasouli et al., 2016). Several studies were already been conducted regarding students' e-learning readiness with diverse variables considered in finding out readiness and satisfaction of e-learning implementation before the COVID-19 pandemic. However, few types of research have been explored to investigating the direct link of student's readiness, implementation satisfaction, and attitudes towards e-learning on their academic performance. Most studies were done overseas, and quite a few were conducted locally.

Aboagye et al. (2020) and Alipio's (2020) studies on the e-learning readiness of higher education learners in less economically developed countries like Ghana and the Philippines during the COVID-19 pandemic found out that students in both countries were not ready for online learning, which centers on internet connectivity issues respectively. A clear indication that internet infrastructure, among other concerns, is quite a pressing issue in most developing countries of the world. At the same time, Ali's (2020) findings showed that higher educational institutions worldwide are directing their collective efforts toward online learning or e-learning, which is vital in times of lockdowns and the observance of basic health protocols such as social distancing. Moreover, financial and material resources, staff readiness, confidence, student accessibility, and motivation play a vital function in the information communication technology integrated or ICT learning. Oye et al. (2012), as cited by Elfaki et al. (2019) in a pre-COVID19 study, believe that e-learning has a positive impact on the academic achievements of students in terms of reduces costs, saving time, and increases the accessibility of education as well as enhances academic performance.

Considering the foregoing assertions on on-line learning, this research may help identify or determine students' readiness or perceptions on e-learning that may affect students' academic performance. Hence, through the current research findings, suggestions and interventions will be crafted to help improve students' academic performance via e-learning which could be implemented and facilitated by the teachers and their higher education institutions or HEI's respectively.

Research Objectives

This research was conducted to assess the readiness of students in the e-learning approach during the COVID-19 pandemic. Basically, this study determined the students' readiness, attitudes, implementation of e-learning, and its impact on academic achievement.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive-correlational-causal research design, and a universal sampling technique was used, using a survey questionnaire to evoke information from participants. Descriptive research aims to accurately and systematically describe a population, situation, or phenomenon while correlational research measures the relationship between two variables (McCombes, 2019).

The instruments used to obtain the necessary data was an adapted survey questionnaire developed by Mercado (2008), modified by Doculan (2016) in her research study regarding assessment tools for e-learning readiness of Philippine higher education institutions. Additionally, for the student satisfaction of e-learning implementation, the researcher adapted a researcher-modified questionnaire of Vitoria et al. (2018), patterned after that of Davis F.D. et al., (1989) Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), which centered on students' perceptions of e-learning implementation focusing on two dimensions namely; perceived of usefulness and perceived ease of use.

After getting the necessary approval, the researcher administered the questionnaire via Google Forms which is considered appropriate considering its wide reach and the different locations of the students employed in the present study and the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic. The data gathered were processed and analyzed using SPSS software.

The study was conducted at Gingoog City Colleges, Paz Village Gingoog City, during 2020-2021. Gingoog City Colleges is a non-sectarian, private institution offering primary education, junior high school, and senior high school and college courses. As an institutional response to the COVID-19 pandemic, the school adopted a blended learning modality in its elementary and junior high school departments, respectively, while the college department conducted classes entirely in an online modality beginning first semester of the SY 2020-2021

The study population were the 154 first-year Criminology students who were officially enrolled in the subject handled by the researcher, particularly the General Education Subject number 3 for the School Year 2020-2021.

Results and Discussion

This study was conducted to assess the readiness of 1st year Criminology students of Gingoog City Colleges in the e-learning approach during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study aimed to determine the students' readiness, attitudes, implementation of e-learning, and its impact on academic achievement. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following questions: (1) What is the level of students' readiness for the e-learning teaching approach? (2) What is the students' level of satisfaction in the e-learning implementation? (3) What is the level of student's attitudes towards a successful online learner? (4) What is the level of academic performance of the students in Social Science? (5) Is there a significant relationship between the students' academic performance, e-learning readiness, implementation satisfaction, and attitudes towards E-Learning? (6) Which of the variables best influence academic performance?

There were 134 1st year Criminology students who participated in the study in descriptive-correlational-causal research. Mean, Standard Deviation, Pearson Product-Moment Correlation, and Multiple Regression were the statistical tools used in the study.

Results of the study revealed that the overall mean for students' readiness on e-learning is 3.34, interpreted as moderately ready on the e-learning teaching approach at the time of the pandemic. These findings support the result of the study conducted by Alipio (2020) regarding learners' readiness for e-learning in a less-economically developed country like the Philippines during COVID-19, where the majority of the respondents had no access to a computer with an Internet connection and adequate software (e.g., Microsoft Word, Adobe Acrobat).

Likewise, the overall mean for students' level of satisfaction in the e-learning implementation is 3.63, interpreted as highly satisfied which revealed that the students were delighted with the e-learning implementation of their school. This finding supports the findings of Vitoria et al. (2018), in which, being familiar with the Internet, the students claimed they knew how to access the source materials online. Moreover, the finding is also parallel to Al-Dosari's (2011) findings, as cited by Vitoria et al. (2018), online course users considered accessibility to be the most significant advantage of e-learning.

Moreover, the overall mean for students' attitudes on e-learning is 3.77, interpreted as highly positive which showed that the students who took part in this study were highly optimistic about the e-learning platform. The finding conforms with Tuntirojanawong's (2013) findings, which indicated that overall, attitudes were rated as having ready status suggesting that students were ready to join an e-learning program and will likely succeed due to their effective study habits being motivated, and appropriate time management skills.

In terms of academic performance, the overall mean is 2.5 (81% to 82%), which revealed that the academic performance in Social Science was described as good

In terms of the significant relationship between the students' academic performance, e-learning readiness, implementation satisfaction, and attitudes towards e-learning, data revealed that students' readiness for e-learning ($P(0.68) > 0.05$) and satisfaction with e-learning implementation ($P(0.85) > 0.05$) were not significantly related to their academic performance in Social Science. In contrast, students' attitudes on e-learning ($P(0.026) < 0.05$) showed a significant relationship to academic performance in the said subject.

In terms of the variables that best influence academic performance, the data revealed that only students' attitude on e-learning ($P(0.026) < 0.05$) has a significant relationship to academic performance in social science. On the other hand, students' attitudes toward e-learning ($P(0.003) < 0.05$) significantly influence academic performance in Social Science.

Conclusions

Majority of the respondents who took part in this study were not entirely ready and were hesitant about e-learning. In addition, the school officials effectively implemented the school's e-learning platform as perceived by the participants. The student-participants accepted and were hopeful of the e-learning modality under the new normal. However, the student-participants have struggled academically in Social Science. Students with a positive attitude towards e-learning have better showing in social science. Students who have a positive attitude towards e-learning could achieve a better performance in Social Science.

The school officials may consider conducting orientation to the students on the relevance of e-learning under the new normal.

The school officials are encouraged to improve its e-learning platform implementation by addressing the needs of the students, such as internet connectivity and others.

The school officials may consider conducting hands-on or workshops to enhance their understanding on e-learning tools.

The faculty members may consider using varied forms of learning modalities to supplement the e-learning platform.

The researchers interested in re-conducting this study are encouraged to explore other variables that can significantly affect academic performance in social science.

The school officials in charge of student services are encouraged to conduct a seminar/webinar on the importance of having a positive attitude.

The school may consider an admin-student consultation conducted in every department at least once a week to address students' concerns regarding e-learning in the new normal via ZOOM, GMEET, or FB LIVE.

The school administration, with the support of different stakeholders, may formally write a letter of appeal to the Commission on Higher Education Region X as well as the office of the Department of Information and Communications Technology to formulate policies urging internet telecommunication companies to address the pressing issues on internet connectivity in Gingoog and the surrounding municipalities. Thus, facilitating a more reasonable internet connection for students attending online classes in the midst of the pandemic.

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